

**Definite
CCRI**

 Ref. Ares(2023)712344 - 31/01/2023

DEFINITE-CCRI

Gender Equality and Inclusivity Plan

Deliverable 1.4

Work Package 1

31/01/2023

**Funded by
the European Union**

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or REA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Deliverable Number	D 1.4
Deliverable Name	Gender Equality and Inclusivity Plan
Full Project Title	DEFINITE-CCRI - Deal Engine, with finance, investment and technical expertise for the Circular Cities and Regions Initiative
Due date of deliverable	31.01.2023
Actual submission date	31.01.2023
Dissemination level	Public (PU)
Author(s)	Nuha Eltinay (ICLEI), Alina Mures (ICLEI), Alessandra Barbieri (ICLEI); Roman Mendle (ICLEI)
Reviewer(s)	Kristen Strandberg (CE), Tommaso Buso (BwB), Eleni Kanelou (NTUA), Dieter DeSmedt (COG)
Contributor(s)	All partners
WP/Task related to the deliverable	WP1/Task 1.6
Document ID	DEFINITE-CCRI_ Gender Equality and Inclusivity plan
Abstract	This document discloses measures and actions implemented across the project's activities to promote Gender equality and social inclusivity.

Cite as: N. Eltinay (ICLEI), A. Mures (ICLEI), A. Barbieri (ICLEI); R. Mendle (ICLEI) (2023). DEFINITE-CCRI PDA-EU. Gender Equality and Inclusivity Plan (Deliverable 1.4.).

DEFINITE Consortium Partners

Logo	Organisation	Type	Country
	ICLEI EURO	Small and medium-sized enterprise	Germany
	Circle Economy	Non-governmental organisation	The Netherlands
	Stad Gent	Municipality	Belgium
 National Technical University of Athens	National Technical University of Athens (NTUA)	University	Greece
	Bankers without Boundaries (BwB)	Non-governmental organisation	United Kingdom

Table of Contents

<u>LIST OF FIGURES</u>	6
<u>LIST OF TABLES</u>	6
<u>LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS</u>	6
<u>EXECUTIVE SUMMARY</u>	6
<u>1. SUMMARY OF DEFINITE-CCRI</u>	7
<u>2. GENERAL STATEMENT</u>	8
<u>3 INTRODUCTION</u>	10
<u>4.1 INTERNAL COMPONENT: MEASURES IMPLEMENTED IN THE PROJECT CONSORTIUM</u>	11
<u>4.1.1 TO ENSURE AN EQUAL SHARE OF REPRESENTATION ACROSS THE GENDER SPECTRUM</u>	11
<u>4.1.3 TO PROMOTE ARRANGEMENTS THAT ENSURE AN EQUITABLE DISTRIBUTION OF WORKLOAD ACROSS STAFF IN DEFINITE-CCRI</u>	15
<u>4.2.1 WORK PACKAGE 2 - CITY AND INVESTOR ENGAGEMENT AND PROJECT SELECTION</u>	16
<u>4.2.3 PACKAGE 3 - FINANCIAL AND LEGAL PROJECT DEVELOPMENT ASSISTANCE</u>	17
<u>4.2.3 WORK PACKAGE 4 - TECHNOLOGICAL PROJECT DEVELOPMENT ASSISTANCE</u>	18
<u>4.2.4 WORK PACKAGE 5 - PROJECT BANKABILITY APPRAISAL AND DEAL BROKERAGE</u>	18

<u>4.2.5 WORK PACKAGE 6 - COMMUNICATION, REPLICATION AND EXPLOITATION</u>	<u>19</u>
<u>5. COUNTERING SEXUAL HARASSMENT, BULLYING, AND DISCRIMINATION</u>	<u>20</u>
<u>6. CONCLUSION</u>	<u>20</u>

List of figures

Figure 1 Overall gender balance across DEFINITE-CCRI consortium

Figure 2 Staff in DEFINITE-CCRI by gender and partner organization

Figure 3 Percentage of staff by gender and seniority level in the DEFINITE-CCRI Team

List of Tables

Table 1 Number of women and men by consortium partner

Table 2 Distribution of staff by gender and seniority level in the DEFINITE-CCRI Team

Table 3 Estimated workload per gender, in percentage terms, over the project lifetime

List of abbreviations

- BwB – Bankers without Boundaries Connect CLG
- CCRI - Circular Cities and Regions Initiative
- CE – Stichting Circle Economy
- CoG - Stad Gent
- EU - European Union
- ICLEI – Local Governments for Sustainability
- NTUA – National Technical University of Athens
- PDA - Project Development Assistance
- WP - Work Package

Executive Summary

Transitioning to a circular economy is needed to achieve climate neutrality by 2050 and comply with the global Greenhouse Gas emissions goals set out in the Paris Agreement. The traditional linear economic

model, based on the “take, make, dispose” principles is no longer viable given natural resources constraints, and the social and environmental damages this model brings along. Circular Economy is a transformative opportunity to change current production and consumption patterns, creating economic prosperity, social equity and promoting a regenerative and holistic model that contributes to numerous environmental, economic and social benefits, ranging from improved resource security, reduced GHG emission, new economic opportunities for growth and innovation, new job offers, and better health and safety conditions.

More than 56 percent of the population live in urban areas, a percentage that is expected to double by 2050¹ and to lead cities to be major consumers of natural resources. Indeed, urban centres consume more than 75 percent of natural resources; are responsible for over 50 percent of solid waste; and emit up to 60 percent of GHG at a global level². However, given their proximity to citizens, producers, retailers and service providers, cities can collaborate with different stakeholders (civil society, business, research centres) to foster transition to a circular economy, and benefit not only the environment, but also the urban community.

For the transition to a circular economy to be fair and just, it has to support the participation of women across the *entire* circular economy spectrum and facilitate the inclusion of the elderly, youth, vulnerable and marginalised groups such as the LGBTIQ+ community, racial minorities, migrants and refugees, and people with special mental and physical capacities in circular economy projects.

In the DEFINITE-CCRI Project we apply a gender lens towards the transition to a just circular economy, and this deliverable thus establishes the Gender Equality and Inclusivity Plan (GEIP) for the project. It aims to strengthen women's leadership and to promote gender equality and women's empowerment, as well as to identify and map the measures and actions that consortium partners will undertake to mainstream gender equality and promote the inclusion of the perspective of vulnerable groups in the consortium and project content.

1. Summary of DEFINITE-CCRI

Effective investment and financing opportunities for circular economy projects in Europe are still few and far in between. Investors need to gain trust in circular economy projects. Projects need to become less risky and bankable, based on new and re-designed finance solutions and business models. Transaction costs need to be decreased and the private finance community needs to be engaged to address legal, administrative and market challenges. The DEFINITE-CCRI project establishes a deal engine, providing technical, financial and circular economy expertise through local project development assistance in an unprecedented and streamlined process to cities, regions and project developers. The deal engine will be built with investors and finance partners and the goal to launch investments in four circular economy

¹ World Bank (2022), <https://www.worldbank.org/en/topic/urbandevelopment/overview>. Accessed 7 January 2023.

²Ellen MacArthur Foundation, *Circular cities: thriving, liveable, resilient*.
<https://ellenmacarthurfoundation.org/topics/cities/overview>. Accessed 7 January 2023.

projects of up to EUR 20 million investment volume per project, amounting to a total portfolio volume of up to EUR 80 million. The DEFINITE-CCRI will demonstrate the bankability of high-impact circularity projects and increases maturity and investor trust in circular economy innovation. It closes the gap between project developers in cities and regions on one side, and investors and finance partners on the other. The DEFINITE-CCRI project co-creates and proves an end-to-end PDA process, aggregating risk mitigation, EU Taxonomy compliance, circularity criteria and technical and financial engineering in a single project development service for the CCRI's service portfolio. Partners commit to operate the deal-engine sustainably beyond the project lifetime. This will inject the financial, technical and managerial know-how into urban circular transitions and ultimately contribute to lower virgin non-renewable material use, lower GHG emissions and more just and inclusive circular employment in line with the European Green Deal, the Circular Economy Action Plan and the Bio-economy Strategy

The project DEFINITE-CCRI will support the CCRI by creating a project development assistance (PDA) instrument to deliver bankable projects to investors and thereby actively contribute to the implementation of the European Green Deal, the Circular Economy Action Plan and the Bio-economy strategy in practice, demonstrating the financial viability—and reducing risk of—circular economy investments.

The project will follow the deal engine methodology described below:

- Step 1: **Technical and impact potential** - Initial screening to determine their suitability to advance in line with EU strategies and plans.
- Step 2: **Finance and investment baseline** - Screening in regards to financial models and investment plans in line with financial instruments and finance and investor requirements identified.
- Step 3: **Due diligence support** - Support in preparing all necessary documents and information input required to submit a finance or investment proposal application to suitable investors partnering with DEFINITE-CCRI.
- Step 4: **Project appraisal** - The consortium organises a project appraisal event for each project, inviting finance and investment partners of DEFINITE-CCRI and project stakeholders as identified by the local project owner
- Step 5: **Deal brokerage** - All projects with a DEFINITE-CCRI stamp of approval will be submitted to suitable investors to take up contracting negotiations and formalities. Outcomes, learnings and experiences will be documented and disseminated via communication and capacity building activities

2. General Statement

Recognizing the urgency for women's participation and the inclusion of various vulnerable and marginalized groups in the transition to a circular economy system stem from the need to create a more sustainable, comprehensive, and just model to provide systemic solutions.

Gender socialisation and the gender discriminatory division of labour continue to preserve the unbalanced distribution of power and inequality in the transition to the circular economy. As a matter of fact, researchers claim that women and men have different consumption and production patterns³. On the one hand, the marginalisation of women from leadership positions has led male-driven production choices to reach unsustainable levels leading to numerous environmental, economic, and social damages, the effects of which have a greater impact on women and socially disadvantaged groups⁴. On the other hand, data show that women tend to work predominantly in low-value-added, informal, and end-of-pipe circular economy activities, including recycling, reuse, and waste management, that according to the OECD, lead women to suffer from poor job security, economic instability, dependence on limited natural resources for survival, and exposure to harmful products and chemicals⁵. And, while women are predominant in low economic value activities, social and political structures have given them limited opportunities to participate in research and innovation activities related to circular economy⁶. Therefore, failure to include a gender perspective in research activities on the transition to a circular economy risks perpetuating gender discrimination and conducting incomplete studies and analyses.

However, despite the fact that the discriminatory division of labour has relegated women to family and domestic life and to performing unpaid reproductive work (housekeeping, care, cleaning and cooking, among others) - it has also forced them to optimize the performance of these tasks - minimizing costs and maximizing the use of the resources at their disposal - thus making them more sensitive to ecological, environmental and health concerns⁷ and prone to adopt more sustainable consumption behaviours⁸.

Acknowledging such differences brings along the need to foster the development of gender-sensitive and socially responsive circular economy projects while incentivizing women's empowerment as consumers, producers, and decision-makers to accelerate the transition to a circular economy. Analysing and considering such differences help understand how circular economy strategies can facilitate women's participation and inclusivity, promote new economic and job opportunities, as well as reduce informal economy, thus paving the way to sustainable development to mitigate climate change impacts⁹.

The DEFINITE-CCRI consortium values gender equality and recognizes the need to foster a fair and equitable circular economy transition. Therefore, the objective of the following Gender Equality and Inclusivity plan are the following:

- To improve gender balance and inclusive participation in the consortium composition.

³ OECD (2021), *Gender and the Environment: Building Evidence and Policies to Achieve the SDGs*, OECD Publishing, Paris, <https://doi.org/10.1787/3d32ca39-en>.

⁴ Albaladejo M et al. (2022), *Why adopting a gender inclusive approach towards Circular Economy matters*. <https://iap.unido.org/articles/why-adopting-gender-inclusive-approach-towards-circular-economy-matters#fn-1286-0>. Industrial Analytics Platform.

⁵ OECD (2020), *Gender-specific consumption patterns, behavioural insights, and circular economy*. <https://www.oecd.org/env/GFE-Gender-Issues-Note-Session-5.pdf>. Accessed 7 January 2023.

⁶ Albaladejo M et al. (2022), *Why adopting a gender inclusive approach towards Circular Economy matters*.

⁷ OECD (2020), *Gender-specific consumption patterns, behavioral insights, and circular economy*. Page 3.

⁸ Albaladejo M et al. (2022), *Why adopting a gender inclusive approach towards Circular Economy matters*

⁹UNCTAD (2020), *Mainstreaming gender equality in investment promotion*. <https://unctad.org/webflyer/mainstreaming-gender-equality-investment-promotion>

- To promote gender equality and social inclusivity in the contents and activities developed within the project, including webinars, events, and research activities in general.

3 Introduction

The European Union has strengthened its commitment to gender equality as a cross-cutting priority in research and innovation activities and aims to eliminate gender and intersecting socio-economic inequalities¹⁰.

DEFINITE-CCRI seeks to develop a project development assistance mechanism to support innovative circular economy projects. The project started in November 2022 and will end in April 2025. And, while it contributes to the EU Green Deal, the EU Circular Economy Action Plan, and the Bio-economy strategy to support the transition towards circular economy in cities and regions, it has a high potential to promote more just and inclusive circular employment opportunities.

As claimed in the General Statement, the Circular Economy creates outstanding social benefits in terms of increased human well-being, new job opportunities and improved health and safety conditions¹¹. And by adopting and internalising concepts such as sustainability, gender and social inclusion, it attracts sustainable finance and incentivise investments¹² thus further strengthening the pathway toward a comprehensive and 'just transition'.

Therefore, in line with the EU commitment to gender inclusivity, the DEFINITE-CCRI Gender Equality and Inclusivity Plan formulates key objectives and measures to achieve equal treatment between women and men across the project consortium and promote gender equality and social-cultural inclusivity in all the activities implemented in the project.

The aim of the Gender Equality and Inclusivity Plan is to ensure that the team composition approximates an equal share of representation across the gender spectrum as well as to promote inclusivity, visibility, accessibility and active engagement across the project's activities. Aiming to support the elaboration of a robust project development assistance mechanism, in the development of the deal engine and expected evaluation of the project's impact on the interested communities. DEFINITE-CCRI will address communities and groups that are mostly affected by the current productive system. Some of the vulnerable groups that DEFINITE-CCRI will address are elderly, youth, marginalised groups such as the LGBTIQ+ community, racial minorities, migrants and refugees, as well as people with special mental and physical capacities.

This document focuses on measures and actions to promote gender mainstreaming internally - in terms of gender balance and inclusivity in the project consortium - and externally - in terms of mainstreaming gender and social inclusivity measures across the project activities engaging the project's stakeholders and the public.

4 DEFINITE-CCRI approach to promote gender mainstreaming

¹⁰ Burg, M. V. D. (2021). FR2. 1: *Gender equality- A strengthened commitment in Horizon Europe*.

¹¹ Bacova, M. et al. (2016). *Pathways to a circular economy in cities and regions. Interreg Europe Joint Secretariat: Lille, France*.

¹² Schröder, P. and Raes, J (2021). *Financing an inclusive circular economy: De-risking investments for circular business models and the SDGs*. Chatham House.

Each partner organization involved in DEFINITE-CCRI is committed to promoting gender equality - in terms of gender participation in the project consortium and teams - and to fostering an inclusive environment across all project activities.

Paragraph 4.1 proposes actions and measures that will be undertaken internally, to ensure that the consortium is gender balanced. Paragraph 4.2 discloses actions and measures that will be implemented across the activities that foresee the engagement of external participants – city representatives, financiers, training participants, etc.

4.1 Internal component: measures implemented in the project consortium

This section explores measures implemented in the consortium to strengthen gender-equal equal representation and participation in the project's implementation and decision-making. Such measures are strongly advised to partners, however, considering the diversity of partner organisations in terms of expertise provided to the project, type of organisation and team compositions, the actions proposed below bring aside the need to be flexible and ensure partners the possibility to deliver the project's main results and outcomes in an efficient manner.

4.1.1 To ensure an equal share of representation across the gender spectrum

The DEFINITE-CCRI consortium is composed of three European non-governmental organizations, an academic institution, and a public institution, as listed below.

- ICLEI Local Governments for Sustainability: a global network of local and regional governments committed to sustainable urban development. ICLEI's staff are responsible for the project coordination, engagement of cities and the mobilisation of a robust project pipeline for the deal engine.
- Bankers without Boundaries (BwB): a not-for-profit finance innovation organisation that provides financial and legal expertise. BwB's staff leads the financial elements related to the design and implementation of the PDA provided by DEFINITE-CCRI to cities, regions, and local project owners.
- Circle Economy (CE): a non-profit impact organization focused on advancing the circular economy. CE's staff contribute to the framing of circular economy concepts, criteria, and guidance for cities and provide expertise in communication and dissemination activities.
- National Technical University of Athens (NTUA) Energy policy Unit: a multidisciplinary scientific and policy consulting department at the National Technical University of Athens (NTUA) that conducts research and development, as well as scientific/technical support. NTUA's role in the

project is to carry out the Technical and Impact Potential assessment of the short-listed projects and provide due diligence support to the owners of the eligible projects.

- City of Ghent (CoG): Belgium's third-largest city and Flanders' biggest University city. CoG aims to advance innovative circular economy solutions, and in DEFINITE-CCRI, its staff leads the capacity-building activities and the establishment of a community of practice. Ghent's participation in the project ensures that the project results are practice-proof and geared towards the needs of cities.

The overall composition of the DEFINITE-CCRI consortium in terms of gender balance among employees of all partner organizations engaged in the project has a ratio of 50:50 (see Figure 1).

Figure 1 Overall gender balance across DEFINITE-CCRI consortium

The project consortium engages a team of around 34 employees, and within each partner organization both genders (female and male) are equally represented across the partner organizations.

The teams of the partner organisations are rather small and variable in terms of numerical composition, ranging from a team three people, as in the case of NTUA, to 15 people for CE, see Figure 2 and Table 1. However, it is important to strengthen that the team's composition may vary during the project, based on the expertise required for the efficient implementation of the project's activities.

Figure 2 Staff in DEFINITE-CCRI by gender and partner organization

Partner organization	Women	Men	Total
BWB	2	2	4
Circle Economy	8	7	15
COG	2	2	4
ICLEI	4	4	8
NTUA	1	2	3
Total	17	17	34

Table 1 Number of women and men by consortium partner

Measure:

- Advocating the inclusion of diverse opinions, experiences and knowledge leads to more innovative ideas, and better decisions, consequently, the project consortium strives to promote gender equality within the team, encourage the active participation and engagement of all staff to create an inclusive environment that respects everyone's views and opinions. The Project Coordinator will, therefore, monitor the composition of the team, and advise project partners to counterbalance potential gender imbalances by promoting a more equitable distribution of capacity and revision the workload allocations where feasible.

4.1.2 To promote gender balance in senior positions

Focusing on women's participation in terms of roles and experience, seniority levels in DEFINITE-CCRI are divided into five main levels, based on the years of seniority (junior level, corresponding to 1 year of experience, middle level corresponding to a work experience of 2 to 3 years, senior level equivalent to 4 to 6 years of experience, coordinator level corresponding to more than 6 years of experience, and a director level equivalent to more than 10 years of seniority). See Table 2.

Gender	Director	Coordinator	Senior	Middle	Junior	Total
Female	1	0	7	7	2	17
Male	2	4	4	4	3	17

Table 2 Distribution of staff by gender and seniority level in the DEFINITE-CCRI Team

Most of the staff working on DEFINITE-CCRI, having experience of up to 6 years, are equally represented in the respective levels of seniority (see Table 3); thus resulting in an equal share of responsibility and engagement. In fact, the seniority levels corresponding to the middle and senior positions entail decision-making power regarding the elaboration and implementation of the project activities and delivery of the project results.

Although women are underrepresented in the highest levels of management and coordination **Error! Reference source not found.**), equivalent to the director and coordinator levels, reflections on their level of engagement in the project implementation is needed. As a matter of fact, for some of the partner organisations, the allocation of work hours to the personnel of those levels may be lower than those allocated to the senior and middle staff, thus leading to lower participation in the project.

Figure 3 Percentage of staff by gender and seniority level in the DEFINITE-CCRI Team

Moreover, in the DEFINITE-CCRI context, the implementation of two important work packages - the development of the project development assistance mechanism and the implementation of the communication activities - are led by female employees from NTUA and CE, having experience equivalent to the senior level and in-depth expertise in their respective fields.

Measure:

- The Project Coordinator will monitor the team composition across the consortium and encourage project partners to promote a more equitable distribution of capacity, by revising the workload allocations where feasible and promoting an equal share of responsibilities across the project's activities.

4.1.3 To promote arrangements that ensure an equitable distribution of workload across staff in DEFINITE-CCRI

The DEFINITE-CCRI consortium is committed to ensuring gender-equal treatment in the distribution of capacity. Considering that the DEFINITE-CCRI project is in its third month since it started, in November 2022, Table 3 depicts the estimated percentages of capacity per gender, over the project lifetime, based on an initial estimate, which will be further monitored in the reporting periods foreseen for month 18 and month 30.

Gender	BWB	CE	ICLEI	NTUA
Female	50%	55%	70%	40%
Male	50%	45%	30%	60%

Table 3 Estimated workload per gender, in percentage terms, over the project lifetime

As illustrated in Table 3, four of the partner organisations foresee an overall fair allocation of capacity for the implementation of activities, with the exception of the small NTUA team; where, as mentioned above, only one senior female employee is involved in the project, being responsible for the development of the PDA mechanism. The fifth entity, not mentioned in the table, the City of Ghent (COG) is responsible for the implementation of activities and the development of a Community of Practice for cities, partners, and external stakeholders. Considering that the respective tasks have not started yet, as they depend on the selection of cities and the development of the Deal Engine steps, and given the specificity of the tasks, for which a higher number of employees may be required, an estimation of the expected workload is not feasible at this stage of the project.

Measure

- If imbalances in allocated capacity occur during the reporting periods, project partners are advised to review workload distribution, where possible, and promote a fair distribution of responsibilities and engagement in the project's activities.

The Gender Equality and Inclusivity Plan will be updated and monitored during the course of the project, and more specifically in Month 18, and Month 24 through a shared questionnaire.

4.2 External components: measures implemented across project activities

Although gender does not represent a specific research topic in DEFINITE-CCRI - except for the deliverable on the project's Gender Equality and Inclusivity plan - we strive to include the gender perspective and diversity of views as a transversal topic across work packages. As a matter of fact, many of the activities envisaged in the project foresee the engagement or consultation of external stakeholders and the communication of the project's results to a wider audience. We consider these elements as an opportunity to achieve a better understanding of gender issues and promote socio-cultural diversity to foster the development of just and equitable circular economy projects. The following paragraph discloses measures set for work packages meant to include the gender dimension, and promote gender mainstreaming and social inclusivity across the different tasks and activities. Considering that the deal engine mechanism developed under DEFINITE-CCRI will be elaborated during the project lifetime, the measures proposed will be adapted to the needs of such mechanism, and will be further defined during the implementation of the respective work packages.

While the coordinator monitors that the project ensures gender inclusion and respect for diversity of opinions in the consortium, the work package leaders are responsible for applying the measures disclosed below.

4.2.1 Work Package 2 - City and Investor Engagement and Project Selection

The Work Package is dedicated to the development of a template for circular projects and outlines the guiding questions and data requirements for circular economy projects' submissions to DEFINITE-CCRI. The template will be adopted by project owners willing to apply to the deal engine mechanism. Once the project outlines are submitted, the project consortium will engage with cities and local project owners to guide them through the data collection process to generate and improve project outlines, as well as with financiers to identify financial institutions or funds suitable for forming the ideal investor base.

Measures:

- In developing the template for circular economy project outlines, WP contributors will include questions on gender and socio-economic inclusivity activities for project owners such as the following indicative examples:
 - How are you planning to promote gender inclusivity and/or gender equality in the project and in your organisation? Please briefly explain.
 - Do you have a Gender Equality Plan? Yes/No. If yes, please link/upload it.
 - Will the project benefit any of the following groups: gender, elderly, youth, vulnerable and marginalised groups such as racial minorities, LGBTIQ+ community, migrants and

- refugees, people with special mental and physical capacities? If yes, what are the anticipated benefits?
- Further relevant gender-related and social inclusivity questions will be developed, if necessary, and they will be included in the project outlines.
- Among the data collected across the projects submitted to the DEFINITE-CCRI deal engine, sex-disaggregated statistics on social and economic dimensions may be included to understand the socio-economic impact of submitted projects.

WP contributors will screen asset managers and general investor categories as to how far they respect the minimum requirements in terms of gender equality, gender balance across investments, and similar considerations. Additionally, upon agreement on the topic, if several investors are interested in deploying capital on projects identified by the DEFINITE-CCRI deal engine, WP contributors may give preferential or priority treatment and access to gender-inclusive funds or investors in order to maintain a high gender equality standard among all the participants in the project.

4.2.3 Package 3 - Financial and Legal Project Development Assistance

DEFINITE-CCRI consortium partners will develop a financial due diligence process, by elaborating the knowledge base and methodological framework of the financial and legal related elements of the DEFINITE-CCRI deal engine. The procedure will allow selected project owners to undertake the Project Development Assistance (PDA) procedure and receive Financial Due Diligence assistance. Work Package contributors will assess projects' Financial and Investment Baseline (FIB), as well as financial risk factors, and provide them with direct support and recommendations to mitigate the financial and legal project risks, improve business plans and prepare for tendering procedures or select appropriate financial instruments.

Measures:

- Leveraging the data and inclusivity feedback gathered as part of WP2, gender considerations will be incorporated into the financial due diligence methodology to reflect gender inclusion as a risk mitigation tool – given the important role that women and other diverse groups play within the circular economy it would stand to reason that greater inclusivity would help to increase the probability of success of the project.
- When implementing the PDAs, the project consortium will highlight any conclusions on gender and how this affects the technical components of the project and its potential bankability; any conclusions will be incorporated into the support and recommendations provided to the prospect projects as part of the iterative process between DEFINITE-CCRI and prospect projects.

Consideration of gender inclusivity as a means of widening the possible investor base to tap into ESG and other social / gender focused investment funds / vehicles.

4.2.3 Work Package 4 - Technological Project Development Assistance

The Project Development Assistance (PDA) provided to the selected projects consists of assessing the Technical and Impact Potential (TIP), the technical feasibility of the local project outlines, and the Key Performance Indicators, taking into consideration their environmental, social and macro-economic impacts. After the initial assessment, cities and local project owners will be supported in improving the technical components required to increase their bankability, develop the feasibility studies or organizing stakeholder mobilisation. The PDA will be based on the development of a methodological framework of the technology and impact-related components of the DEFINITE-CCRI deal engine.

Measures:

- When developing the knowledge base and methodological framework of the technology, the gender and inclusivity dimensions will be taken into account, by examining how they are considered in the existing methodologies and assessment criteria for PDA. The framework will be applied to the shortlisted projects within the DEFINITE-CCRI approach, by taking into consideration the local context and the specificities of the projects.
- When assessing the Technical and Impact potential of the selected projects undertaking the PDA, WP contributors will investigate among others:
 - How gender, elderly and youth, and marginalised/vulnerable groups such as the LGBTIQ+ community, racial minorities, migrants and refugees, and people with special mental and physical capacities are impacted by the proposed project at a local level by considering for instance their level of engagement.
 - How the project will affect women and members of the local community as consumers, and in general, how women and marginalised groups are taken into account within the restrictions of the PDA;
- How potential KPIs considered in the project are inclusive, by defining the target groups, measuring the stakeholder elicitation and co-creation processes from a gender engagement perspective or/and using gender-focused indicators. The project will highlight how the gender dimension is taken into account in the PDA and how this affects the technical components of the project and its potential bankability.
- Taking into account gender in identifying subcontracting needs for data provision or similar requirements to be handled by local stakeholders or project owners.

4.2.4 Work Package 5 - Project Bankability Appraisal and Deal Brokerage

The revision of the technological, impact and financial due diligence outcomes from WP3 & WP4, will lead to the final project appraisal with project owners and investors for the developed projects. DEFINITE-CCRI consortium partners will facilitate investor contracting after project appraisal with project owners. Finally, the methodological and operational elements developed for the deal engine will

be consolidated in the form of a project evaluation tool for further application by cities beyond DEFINITE-CCRI.

Measures:

- To perform an additional round of review of gender criteria of unselected projects which, upon the re-entrance to the deal engine, will also be able to adjust and improve their gender considerations in the direct management and review of all their internal processes, to increase their likelihood of receiving a stamp of approval.
- As the projects establish MRV processes, cities will be required to establish, review and verify procedures that include gender-centred criteria, with specific attention to the way workload is divided, and to groups of the population that are mostly affected by the choices of project leaders.
- Despite the project tools and guidebook being mostly related to financial criteria, such evaluation tools will remain conditional to the approval of other consortium members. Recommendations for gender considerations, gender inclusion, work distribution and MRV processes across the relevant project lifecycle will be given.

4.2.5 Work Package 6 - Communication, Replication and Exploitation

The implementation of communication and dissemination activities foresee the development of a communication plan and a dedicated web portal for the DEFINITE-CCRI Deal engine partners and stakeholders. Among the different activities, project partners will implement a capacity-building program for cities and regions adhering to the Circular Cities and Regions Initiative, PDA service providers, local project owners, and public audiences to improve their knowledge of how to secure funding for circular projects in cities, address circular economy impact, and the gender perspective and diversity and inclusivity as core criteria for sustainable project preparation. Finally, project partners will organize a community of practice on circular economy project finance to incentivize the development of an ecosystem of external PDA providers beyond the CCRI consortium and to provide an exchange platform for project owners, cities, and investors.

Measures:

- WP contributors will adopt gender-sensitive language and practices in all communication activities (e.g., articles and press releases, webinars, events, social media posts, public reports, etc.). Guidelines on gender-sensitive language will be distributed to the project's partners.
- WP contributors will avoid gender stereotypes and encourage a broad inclusion of different age groups as well as vulnerable and marginalised groups in images, photos and videos.
- WP contributors will make sure to include different gender perspectives in discussions, providing equal space and power to all genders. WP contributors will ensure gender balance in communication activities, making sure that all genders are represented as speakers in workshops, conferences, forums, and other events and when interviewing people for a video.

5. Countering sexual harassment, bullying, and discrimination

DEFINITE-CCRI rejects any form of discrimination or harassment and promotes a work culture of inclusion and mutual respect. In organizing project events, project partners are committed to creating an inclusive, respectful and safe environment. All participants are expected to conduct themselves with integrity and respect toward all those who participate or are involved in the events.

Measure:

- DEFINITE-CCRI consortium partners commit to counter sexual harassment, bullying and discrimination in the project consortium teams, as well as in the events organized during the project's lifetime. To this end, we will adopt a Code of Conduct valid for project consortium and public events. The Code of Conduct will be shared with speakers and participants of the events organized and it will be shared on the project website. The details of the Code of Conduct will be elaborated in the following months.

6. Conclusion

All the entities involved in DEFINITE-CCRI shall pay particular attention to gender issues, with the aim to be actively involved in the development of the Gender Equality Plan measures to be implemented, and committed to the measures proposed above for each Work Package to be applied throughout the life of the project.

Although DEFINITE-CCRI does not directly consider gender issues as a research topic, it takes into account gender dynamics both in the composition of the consortium and in the implementation of project activities and content.

DEFINITE-CCRI consortium is generally gender balanced, and each partner involves staff on equal footing with a fair distribution of capacity and responsibility in the implementation of the project across the gender spectrum. Project consortium partners strive to mainstream the gender dimension and promote social inclusivity across all work packages by realizing the measures indicated above and monitoring their achievements across the project's lifetime.

The project consortium will elaborate and commit to a project's Code of Conduct - against sexual harassment, bullying, and discrimination - that will be published on the DEFINITE-CCRI project website together with the Gender Equality Plan.